

NAVIGATING THE UNCHARTED TERRITORY: A HOLISTIC REVIEW OF mRNA VACCINE

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ABSTRACT

The introduction of mRNA vaccines represents a innovative milestone within the discipline of vaccinology, imparting a promising road for combatting infectious diseases. This complete assessment delves into the intricacies of mRNA vaccines, protecting numerous aspects from their underlying mechanisms to their worldwide effect. The article starts off evolved via way of means of elucidating the essential standards of the way mRNA vaccines work, dropping mild at the approaches worried in harnessing the body's vital exploration of the developmental trajectory of mRNA vaccines follows, inspecting the important thing milestones and breakthroughs which have paved the manner for his or her fast deployment. The assessment additionally categorizes and compares extraordinary mRNA vaccine platforms, offering insights into their layout versions and ability packages. An in-intensity evaluation of efficacy and protection profiles constitutes a pivotal section, synthesizing findings from medical trials and real-global packages. The emergency use and approval of mRNA vaccines are mentioned in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, highlighting the extended regulatory pathways and the worldwide reaction to the unparalleled fitness crisis. The article explores the worldwide effect of mRNA vaccines, emphasizing their position in shaping public fitness techniques and mitigating the unfold of infectious diseases. Addressing not unusual place misconceptions surrounding this subject matter is crucial in fostering public knowledge and trust, and this assessment pursuits to dispel everyday myths thru evidence-primarily totally based information. As the panorama of mRNA vaccines keeps evolving, the item concludes via way of means of inspecting destiny traits within the discipline, along with ongoing research, ability packages Ethical issues surrounding the usage of mRNA primarily totally based vaccines also are deliberated, spotting the significance of moral frameworks in guiding their accountable deployment. This assessment serves as a complete useful resource for researchers, healthcare professionals, and policymakers, imparting a nuanced angle at the contemporary state, challenges, and potentialities of mRNA vaccines.

Keywords: mRNA vaccine, COVID-19, Vaccine market, Vaccine development.

INTRODUCTION

Vaccines play a crucial role in preventing countless illnesses and saving numerous lives annually [1]. Thanks to the widespread use of vaccines, we've witnessed the complete eradication of the smallpox virus and a significant reduction in the occurrence of diseases like polio and measles worldwide [2]. Nucleic acid therapeutics, particularly in the form of in vitro transcribed (IVT) mRNA, have emerged as promising alternatives to traditional vaccine approaches. Back in 1990, researchers reported successful experiments with IVT mRNA in animals, demonstrating the creation of proteins after injecting reporter gene mRNAs into mice [3]. Subsequent studies in 1992 showed that introducing vasopressin-encoding mRNA in the hypothalamus triggered a physiological response in rats [4]. Despite these early promising results, concerns about mRNA instability, innate immunogenicity, and inefficient in vivo delivery hindered substantial investment in mRNA therapeutics.

Over the past decade, however, significant technical innovations and research expenditures have transformed mRNA into a viable tool for vaccine development and protein replacement therapy. mRNA offers several advantages over other vaccine types, such as subunit, killed and live attenuated virus, as well as DNA-based vaccines. Firstly, in terms of safety, mRNA is a non-infectious, non-integrating platform, eliminating the potential risk of infection or insertional mutagenesis. Moreover, mRNA undergoes natural physiological processes for destruction, and its in vivo half-life can be controlled through different modifications and delivery mechanisms [5-8]. The inherent immunogenicity of mRNA can be modulated to enhance its safety profile [5,8,9]. Secondly, in terms of efficacy, various modifications make mRNA more stable and highly translatable [5,8,9]. Efficient in vivo delivery is possible by formulating mRNA into carrier molecules, facilitating rapid uptake and expression in the cytoplasm. As a minimal genetic vector, mRNA avoids anti-vector immunity, allowing for repeated administration of mRNA vaccines. Thirdly, in terms of production, the high yields of in vitro transcription processes enable quick, cost-effective, and scalable manufacturing of mRNA vaccines.

The mRNA vaccine field is advancing rapidly, with a wealth of preclinical data accumulated in recent years and numerous human clinical trials initiated. This review delves into current mRNA vaccine approaches, summarizes the latest findings, highlights challenges and recent successes, and provides insights into the future of mRNA vaccines. The data strongly suggest that mRNA vaccines hold immense potential in overcoming challenges in developing vaccines for both infectious diseases and cancer.

Figure 1. Timeline of major events in the history of mRNA

HOW mRNA VACCINES WORK?

mRNA vaccines can be categorized into two main types: conventional mRNA-based vaccines and self-amplifying mRNA vaccines (SAM) (refer to Figure 1). Both types harness the host cell translational machinery to produce the targeted antigen and initiate an adaptive immune response [10-14]. Conventional mRNA vaccines specifically encode the target antigen, functioning in a manner akin to endogenous host cell mRNA molecules. In contrast, SAM vaccines involve encoding an engineered RNA virus genome, often derived from an alphavirus single-stranded, positive sense (+) RNA molecule. This genome contains non-structural proteins (NSPs) and an antigen cassette, effectively replacing the genes responsible for structural proteins [15]. Through RNA template amplification within host cells, these replicons, termed replicons, express the antigen gene in substantial quantities. Importantly, these replicons cannot generate infectious virions or spread to other cells due to the absence of genes encoding viral structural proteins. The alphavirus-based replicon encompasses two open reading frames (ORFs) flanked by untranslated regions (UTRs) at the 5'- and 3'-ends. The first ORF at the 5' end encodes a viral polyprotein, which is cleaved into four NSPs with protease and helicase activities during replication [15,16]. The second ORF, translated from sub-genomic RNA, expresses the antigen, replacing the viral structural proteins. The production of virus-like replicon particles (VRPs) can occur in cell cultures co-expressing viral structural proteins. These replicons have shown efficacy in animal models and immunogenicity in clinical trials [13,17]. Alternatively, synthetic delivery methods may be employed for replicon delivery [10]. In a groundbreaking study in 1993, Martinon et al. [18] demonstrated that mRNA expressing the influenza nucleoprotein, delivered with liposomes, induced an antigen-specific cytotoxic T lymphocytes (CTL) response in mice. Both conventional and self-amplifying mRNA vaccines have demonstrated the ability to prime adaptive immunity, generating antibody-producing B cells, CD4+, and CD8+ T cells. This holds true in homologous modalities as well as in heterologous modalities (prime boost), often in combination with subunit vaccines [10,12,19,20,21]. Protective immunity, characterized by functional antibodies and polyfunctional CD4+ and CD8+ T cells homing to the lungs after respiratory virus infection, has been successfully demonstrated [22,23-24,25].

Figure 2. Mechanism of action of mRNA vaccines

Figure 3. Schematic illustration of difference between self-amplifying RNA and 'conventional' mRNA translation.

DEVELOPMENT OF mRNA VACCINES

In the past ten years, there has been a remarkable surge in global research and development of mRNA vaccines, primarily driven by the urgent need for swift vaccine development in response to emerging diseases like the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic. The World Health Organization (WHO) has played a pivotal role in guiding this effort, employing a specialized tool for prioritizing diseases and pathogens in public health emergency (PHE) situations [26,27]. This list is regularly updated to adapt to evolving needs and methodologies. Based on these priorities, WHO develops research and development roadmaps for each identified disease. The WHO Director-General declared COVID-19 a Public Health Emergency of International Concern in January 2020, later characterizing it as a pandemic in March 2020. mRNA vaccines emerged as frontrunners in clinical development during this crisis, showcasing approximately 95% efficacy in Phase 3 clinical trials [28,29]. These vaccines have received emergency use approval from national regulatory authorities in certain countries to combat the pandemic [30,31]. Notably, on December 31, 2020, the WHO granted emergency use validation to a COVID-19 mRNA vaccine, marking the Pfizer/BioNTech vaccine as the first to receive such recognition [32]. It is anticipated that mRNA vaccines will evolve into a platform technology, providing the ability to rapidly develop vaccines against priority pathogens in PHE scenarios. The use of mRNA as an in-vivo gene-delivery technique was first demonstrated in 1990, showcasing the production of the encoded protein through the direct

injection of "naked" mRNA [33]. However, challenges, such as mRNA instability in vivo due to the presence of RNases, hindered its immediate application. Additionally, the immunogenic nature of mRNA triggered innate responses, reducing mRNA translation. A breakthrough occurred when Karikó and Weissman discovered that modified nucleosides could decrease the immunostimulatory effects of in-vitro transcribed mRNA by reducing Toll-like receptor (TLR) stimulation [34]. The substitution of pseudo uridine for uridine further increased mRNA stability and translational capability [35]. Further advancements by Schlake and colleagues enabled the production of mRNA that avoided innate responses and decreased protein production through sequence engineering, eliminating the need for nucleoside modification [36]. Formulations, primarily lipid nanoparticles (LNPs), have played a crucial role in stabilizing mRNA, aiding its cellular uptake, and facilitating release from endosomes. LNPs, composed of various lipids including phospholipids, cholesterol, ionic lipids, and polyethylene glycol-conjugated lipid, form a structure with an aqueous centre where charged mRNA molecules reside. This ensures mRNA preservation, promotes cellular entry, and aids in the release from lysosomes for efficient mRNA distribution, as demonstrated by Reichmuth and colleagues [37] (and likely to acts as adjuvants for the encoded protein [38]). These developments have propelled the use of mRNA as a platform technology, opening new avenues for rapid and effective vaccine development.

mRNA VACCINE PLATFORM

Establishing a vaccine-based therapy for parasite infections requires evaluation of novel vaccination platform technologies. In this study, we discuss the application of in vitro transcribed (IVT) mRNA vaccines to develop novel vaccines that fend against parasite infections. We will provide a thorough overview of the mRNA vaccine platform and how it relates to the development of mRNA vaccinations to prevent parasite illnesses. In addition to discussing the advantages and disadvantages of the platform for each significant area of vaccine development—manufacturing, formulation, immunology, stability, and safety—we will also discuss the potent immune response that exogenous RNA produces. We will also provide a summary of our approach to creating an mRNA vaccine against Chagas disease and talk about some recently released studies on mRNA vaccines against parasitic diseases. The required product characterizations for the preliminary assessment of mRNA vaccine antigen candidates are reviewed in an accompanying manuscript in this special issue (Poveda et al.) [39]. For further information on mRNA technology beyond its use in parasitic disease treatment, we direct the reader to a few excellent recent reviews on the subject [40-45]. First off, because mRNA vaccines may be translated into the target gene as soon as they enter the cytoplasm of the cell, they do not need to travel all the way to the nucleus, making them more effective and having a better safety profile than viral vector and DNA vaccines. Moreover, they are unable to multiply, cause, introduce mutations, or spread an infection as they are unable to integrate into the host's DNA. By lowering its pro-inflammatory potential, mRNA synthesised with appropriate purification and modified nucleoside incorporation can further improve the safety of mRNA vaccines. Second, because mRNA vaccines can be produced fast, inexpensively, reliably, and without the need for cells, they are the most practical choice for providing life-saving immunizations during a pandemic. Additionally, the translated antigen will naturally display glycosylation and structural traits, which will heighten its immunogenicity. Third, conventional and self-replicating mRNA vaccines in their various forms—naked, adjuvanted, or entrapped in delivery vehicles—have demonstrated remarkable promise in producing neutralising and binding antibodies, eliciting CD4+ and CD8+ cellular responses, fostering memory and long-lasting immunity, and stimulating the innate immune system, which offers the best defence against infectious diseases. In several situations, a single dose of mRNA vaccines was also sufficient to produce protective immunity, underscoring once again the relevance of these vaccines in a pandemic event where mass vaccination is required. [46-48].

EFFICACY AND SAFETY

- ✓ **SIDE EFFECTS AND ADVERSE REACTIONS:** Regarding adverse events, data from phase I influenza mRNA vaccine and phase III COVID-19 mRNA vaccine trials have demonstrated that injection site pain, erythema, swelling, fever, fatigue, headache, chills, muscle pain, and arthralgia are more common in the vaccine group relative to placebo.[49] The majority of individuals in the COVID-19 phase III mRNA-LNP vaccination studies were observed for more than two months, indicating that long-term adverse effects are unlikely. Moderna has enrolled more than 1700 participants in 12 prior Phase I/II studies and has not identified any long-term adverse effects.[50] Long-term adverse effects are unlikely mechanistically, because mRNA does not persist for an extended period or integrate into chromosomes. Thrombosis was frequently reported with any mRNA vaccine, followed by stroke, myocarditis, myocardial infarction, pulmonary embolism, and arrhythmia. [51] other side effects include, Bell palsy, Guillain-Barré syndrome, pulmonary embolism, thrombosis with thrombocytopenia syndrome. [52] Every individual's body response is different than others as it depends on age, sex, race, ethnicity, baseline body-mass index, and the presence of coexisting conditions.

- ✓ **CLINICAL TRIALS RESULTS:** Years of research exploring mRNA vaccines for cancer treatment in preclinical and clinical trials have set the stage for the rapid development of mRNA vaccines during the COVID-19 pandemic.[53] Two nucleic-acid vaccine candidates named MAV E2 and VGX-3100 in 2014 and 2021 completed phase III clinical trials in Mexico and U.S., respectively, for patients with human papillomavirus (HPV)-related, high-grade squamous intraepithelial lesions (HSIL). Their clinical effectiveness, as determined by HSIL regression, was limited in comparison to others.[54]
- ✓ **LONG TERM SAFETY CONSIDERATIONS:** mRNA vaccines have tremendous potential to fight against cancer and viral diseases due to superiorities in safety, efficacy, and industrial production. [55] For mRNA vaccines, tailored administration to the lymph node (LN) is expected to decrease adverse effects and boost the immune response. [56]

EMERGENCY USE AND APPROVAL

The FDA [57] and the EMA [58] granted emergency authorization to Pfizer and BioNTech's mRNA-based vaccination Comirnaty on December 11, 2020 [57], making it the first of its kind. Subsequently, on December 18, 2020 [59] and January 06, 2020, in that order, Moderna's vaccine was given commercial approval by the FDA and the EMA (Figure 4). Currently being evaluated and approved are several additional vaccines by the FDA and EMA. Among these are the COVID-19 vaccine, which was created by Janssen Pharmaceutical Companies (Johnson and Johnson) and their partners, which include Beth Israel Deaconess Medical Centre in Boston, USA, and which was given FDA approval for emergency use on February 28, 2021; additionally, AZD 1222 was created by the University of Oxford in partnership with AstraZeneca and the partners. On January 29, 2021, the European Medicines Agency (EMA) recommended conditional permission for the use of the AZD 1222 vaccination throughout Europe [57–60]. Many of the regulatory requirements that apply to other vaccines also apply to mRNA vaccines, such as the need for standardized manufacturing procedures, superior raw materials, and evidence of safety and efficacy from clinical trials, pre-clinical research, and post-marketing surveillance. A few recent publications [61–63] have discussed regulations related to the safety, quality assurance, and manufacture of mRNA vaccines. On the other hand, vaccination hesitancy jeopardizes the COVID-19 vaccine's adoption and effective pandemic mitigation [64]. Many broad factors, including prior vaccination experience, education and knowledge level, perception of danger and trust, perceived importance of vaccination, subjective standards, and moral and religious convictions, can contribute to reluctance to vaccinate [65]. It's possible that other factors play a role in COVID-19 vaccines. First off, considering how fast the candidates were developed and approved—less than a year—in the public light, some are concerned for their safety. Secondly, there remain numerous unresolved questions regarding the effectiveness of vaccines in halting asymptomatic transmission and the durability of the immune response following immunization, according to clinical investigations [66].

Figure 4. FDA and the EMA approved Moderna's and Pfizer vaccine for sale.

ADDRESSING COMMON MISCONCEPTIONS

- ✓ **BUSTING MYTHS REGARDING mRNA VACCINES:** The complex process of COVID-19 vaccine reluctance is influenced by several factors, including societal, cultural, and individual ones. Understanding mRNA in society and health COVID-19 vaccinations are necessary for the pandemic to be effectively controlled. Healthcare practitioners, such as family doctors and nurses, can assist dispel some myths and reluctance about mRNA COVID-19 vaccinations in the public perception and raise community understanding. [67] Most people were unwilling to get the mRNA COVID-19 vaccine due to false beliefs, fear of immunizations generally having negative consequences, and uncertainty about the long-term implications of immunization, especially among illiterate women. It is the cornerstone of public health's ability to combat false beliefs, anxiety, misunderstandings, vaccine reluctance, and enhance immunization rates.

- ✓ **EQUALIZING MISCONCEPTIONS:** Comparing two studies on Americans who were not vaccinated at two different times after the 2021 vaccine deployment, it was shown that vaccination reluctance was decreased when explanations were given in plain language and misconceptions were cleared up. The control group was given no information. [68] Health officials have recommended avoiding vaccination for anyone with a history of drug allergies or allergies to any component of the vaccine. There are some misconceptions, too, as allergies to certain excipients in drugs and vaccines can occasionally be misdiagnosed due to improper labelling or nomenclature, or because excipients aren't thought to be allergic triggers. [69].

FUTURE DEVELOPMENTS

The need for innovative technology that can produce safe and effective vaccinations quickly and adaptably is growing as new viral pandemics strike the planet every few years. Therefore, the creation of such vaccines represents an urgent unmet therapeutic need. Due to its added advantages over existing vaccination platforms, mRNA-based vaccines are currently the front-runners for various infectious diseases. Promising promise of mRNA technology extends beyond infectious diseases. Among the possible uses are:

- ✓ **Cancer Immunotherapy:** It seeks to alter the suppressive tumour microenvironment and stimulate the host's anti-tumour immunity, which should ultimately lead to a decrease in tumour size and a higher overall patient survival rate. As a promising preventative and therapeutic immunotherapeutic approach, cancer vaccines are an appealing substitute. Because of immunologic memory, vaccinations targeting tumour-associated or tumour-specific antigens (TAAs or TSAs) can selectively target and kill cancerous cells that overexpress the antigens, resulting in a long-lasting therapeutic response. Thus, in comparison to previous immunotherapies, cancer vaccines provide targeted, safe, and acceptable treatment (70).
- ✓ **Therapy Using Protein Replacement:** mRNA for protein replacement therapies can now be generated using the in vitro transcription reaction (IVT) in cell-free systems (71–72). The primary IVT reagents are dNTPs, which act as mRNA building blocks, a DNA-dependent RNA polymerase, a linearized DNA plasmid that functions as a template from which mRNA is to be transcribed, and occasionally a 5' Cap analogue (73).
- ✓ **Regenerative Medicine:** Damaged organs or tissues can be repaired with the use of mRNA, which can be used to rewire cells for tissue regeneration. This method may be used to treat diseases like heart disease or neurological issues.
- ✓ **Allergy Treatment:** It has been demonstrated that allergen-encoding DNA and mRNA vaccines elicit T helper 1 and T regulatory responses, which attenuate or offset allergic T helper 2-biased reactions. mRNA vaccinations may be the best options for prophylactic allergy shots because of their intrinsic safety features (74).

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS

Before being on sale, vaccines are tested on a number of different demographic groups. This is a necessary condition to ensure that a vaccination is effective against "all diverse populations of the world," therefore it's not intrinsically harmful [75]. Nonetheless, a new trend has emerged in which large, international pharmaceutical companies contract out their clinical trials to locations outside than their home state. The outsourced trials typically involve participation from both international and domestic countries. The foreign state consents to participate in "outsourcing trials" to provide treatments that would not otherwise be accessible as part of its healthcare obligations. The state of residency grants permission to participate in studies that are contracted out and comprise a group of international subjects (sometimes referred to as "cross-border clinical trials"), primarily from Brazil, China, and India. Following vaccination, infected patients had elevated IgG antibody levels, supporting the theory that a single vaccination dose—instead of two treatments separated by 21 days—may be adequate to prevent re-infection. However, even for a small number of these individuals, the IgG titers decreased with time, suggesting that, aside from the initial dosage, the remainder of the vaccination regimen should be followed by an uninfected individual. Moreover, the introduction of more recent variants, including Omicron and Delta, may lessen this effect [76]. When it comes to studying the pattern of IgA immune responses after anti-SARS-CoV-2 vaccination and providing strong evidence that IgA levels decline more quickly than IgG levels, our research is, as far as we know, the most comprehensive in the literature. Our results support the early studies by Danese et al. and Wisniewski et al., which discovered that the anti-SARS CoV-2 IgA serum antibody pattern was extremely similar in three and four patients, respectively [77–78]. As mentioned earlier, we discovered that IgA levels were strongly correlated with a history of COVID-19 infection, but not with the age of those who had received vaccinations over time. Several recent projects have focused on the development of intranasal vaccines for anti-SARS-CoV-2 immunisation, which predominantly stimulate mucosal IgA responses to successfully end respiratory infections [79].

GLOBAL IMPACT OF mRNA VACCINE

- ✓ **Pfizer-BioNTech mRNA Vaccine: A Game-Changer In Global Immunization Efforts:** The Pfizer-BioNTech mRNA vaccine has emerged as a game-changer in global immunization efforts, offering a new approach to combatting the COVID-19 pandemic. By utilizing messenger RNA technology, this vaccine has demonstrated high efficacy rates in preventing infection and severe illness. Its ability to be rapidly produced and distributed on a large scale has been crucial in accelerating vaccination campaigns worldwide. The success of the Pfizer-BioNTech vaccine has paved the way for other mRNA vaccines to be developed and deployed, marking a significant shift in how we approach infectious diseases. [80-83]. As countries continue to grapple with the challenges of mass vaccination, the impact of mRNA vaccines is likely to shape future immunization strategies on a global scale. [84]
- ✓ **The Challenges of Global Distribution of the mRNA Vaccine:** One of the main challenges in the global distribution of mRNA vaccines is ensuring equitable access for all countries. High-income nations have secured large quantities of doses, leaving lower-income countries struggling to acquire enough vaccines for their populations. Additionally, mRNA vaccines require ultra-cold storage which presents logistical challenges in regions with limited infrastructure. The cost of transporting and storing these vaccines at such low temperatures further complicates distribution efforts. [85-88]. Furthermore, some countries may lack the necessary healthcare systems to efficiently administer the vaccines to their populations. Addressing these challenges is crucial in order to achieve widespread vaccination coverage and ultimately control the spread of COVID-19 on a global scale. [89,85].
- ✓ **Impact Of mRNA Vaccines on Reducing Covid-19 Transmission Worldwide:** mRNA vaccines have played a crucial role in reducing COVID-19 transmission worldwide by providing a highly effective tool for preventing the spread of the virus. These vaccines have shown remarkable efficacy in preventing severe illness and hospitalization, ultimately leading to a decrease in the overall burden on healthcare systems. By significantly reducing the number of symptomatic cases, mRNA vaccines have helped to break chains of transmission and slow down the spread of COVID-19 within communities. [85-90]. This has not only protected individuals who are vaccinated but also contributed to building herd immunity, making it harder for the virus to find new hosts and continue its rapid spread across borders. [85].
- ✓ **Promising Results and Future Implications of mRNA Vaccines for Global Health:** The promising results of mRNA vaccines have sparked hope for a transformative impact on global health. These innovative vaccines have demonstrated high efficacy rates in preventing COVID-19 and have been praised for their rapid development and ability to adapt to new variants. The success of mRNA vaccines has paved the way for future applications in combating other infectious diseases, such as influenza, HIV, and malaria. [91-93]. Additionally, the scalability and cost-effectiveness of mRNA technology offer opportunities to improve access to vaccines in low- and middle-income countries. As we continue to witness the positive outcomes of mRNA vaccines, the potential for a healthier and more resilient global population is within reach. [94-95].
- ✓ **Collaborative Efforts: International Partnerships Driving the Success of Global Immunization Campaigns:** International partnerships have been instrumental in driving the success of global immunization campaigns using mRNA vaccines. Collaborative efforts between countries, pharmaceutical companies, non-profit organizations, and research institutions have allowed for the rapid development, production, and distribution of these vaccines on a global scale. By sharing resources, knowledge, and technology, these partnerships have accelerated the availability of vaccines to populations around the world. [96,97,85]. Additionally, cross-border collaborations have enabled a more equitable distribution of vaccines to low- and middle-income countries that may not have had access otherwise. These international partnerships underscore the importance of cooperation and solidarity in addressing global health challenges and achieving widespread immunization against infectious diseases. [98-85]

CONCLUSION

Review of mRNA vaccines presented in this comprehensive article navigates through the uncharted territory of this revolutionary technology, shedding light on its underlying mechanisms, developmental trajectory, efficacy, safety profiles, and global impact. The advent of mRNA vaccines represents a milestone in vaccinology, offering a promising avenue for combatting infectious diseases, with a spotlight on their role in the unprecedented COVID-19 pandemic. The article adeptly elucidates the intricate workings of mRNA vaccines, distinguishing between conventional and self-amplifying mRNA platforms and delving into the mechanisms by which they harness the host cell's translational machinery to induce immune responses. The developmental trajectory of mRNA vaccines, fueled by a surge in global research over the past decade, is critically examined. The rapid deployment of mRNA vaccines during the COVID-19 pandemic is explored within the context of emergency use and approval, highlighting accelerated regulatory pathways and global responses. Efficacy and safety profiles are central to the review, synthesizing findings from clinical trials and real-world applications. The

advantages of mRNA vaccines, such as safety, efficacy, and scalable production, are underscored, along with their potential applications beyond infectious diseases, including cancer immunotherapy, protein replacement therapy, regenerative medicine, and allergy treatment. The global impact of mRNA vaccines is analysed in-depth, acknowledging the game-changing role of the Pfizer-BioNTech mRNA vaccine in global immunization efforts. However, challenges in global distribution, equitable access, logistical considerations, and healthcare system capacities are recognized, emphasizing the need for collaborative international efforts to address these issues. Addressing common misconceptions surrounding mRNA vaccines is crucial for fostering public understanding and trust. The review concludes by exploring future developments in the field, including ongoing research, potential applications, and advancements in vaccine technology. Ethical considerations surrounding the use of mRNA vaccines are deliberated, emphasizing the importance of responsible deployment guided by ethical frameworks. In essence, this comprehensive resource provides nuanced insights into the current state, challenges, and prospects of mRNA vaccines, serving as a valuable reference for researchers, healthcare professionals, and policymakers alike. As the landscape of mRNA vaccines continues to evolve, this review contributes to the collective understanding of this groundbreaking technology and its transformative potential for global health.

REFERENCES

1. World Health Organization. Immunization coverage. *World Health Organization* <http://www.who.int/mediacentre/factsheets/fs378/en> (2017).
2. Younger, D. S., Younger, A. P. & Guttmacher, S. Childhood vaccination: implications for global and domestic public health. *Neurol. Clin.* **34**, 1035–1047 (2016).
3. Wolff, J. A. *et al.* Direct gene transfer into mouse muscle *in vivo*. *Science* **247**, 1465–1468 (1990). **This study demonstrates protein production from RNA administered *in vivo*.**
4. Jirikowski, G. F., Sanna, P. P., Maciejewski-Lenoir, D. & Bloom, F. E. Reversal of diabetes insipidus in Brattleboro rats: intrahypothalamic injection of vasopressin mRNA. *Science* **255**, 996–998 (1992).
5. Kariko, K. *et al.* Incorporation of pseudouridine into mRNA yields superior nonimmunogenic vector with increased translational capacity and biological stability. *Mol. Ther.* **16**, 1833–1840 (2008).
6. Kauffman, K. J., Webber, M. J. & Anderson, D. G. Materials for non-viral intracellular delivery of messenger RNA therapeutics. *J. Control. Release* **240**, 227–234 (2016).
7. Guan, S. & Rosenecker, J. Nanotechnologies in delivery of mRNA therapeutics using nonviral vector-based delivery systems. *Gene Ther.* **24**, 133–143 (2017).
8. Thess, A. *et al.* Sequence-engineered mRNA without chemical nucleoside modifications enables an effective protein therapy in large animals. *Mol. Ther.* **23**, 1456–1464 (2015).
9. Kariko, K., Muramatsu, H., Ludwig, J. & Weissman, D. Generating the optimal mRNA for therapy: HPLC purification eliminates immune activation and improves translation of nucleoside-modified, protein-encoding mRNA. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **39**, e142 (2011). **This study demonstrates the importance of purification of IVT mRNA in achieving potent protein translation and in suppressing inflammatory responses.**
10. Ulmer JB, Geall AJ. Recent innovations in mRNA vaccines. *Curr Opin Immunol.* **2016**;41:18–22
11. DeFrancesco L. The ‘anti-hype’ vaccine. *Nat Biotechnol.* **2017**;35 (3):193–197.
12. Ljungberg K, Liljestrom P. Self-replicating alphavirus RNA vaccines. *Expert Rev Vaccines.* **2015**;14(2):177–194.
13. Lundstrom K. Alphavirus-based vaccines. *Viruses.* **2014**;6(6):2392–2415.
14. Kramps T, Elbers K. Introduction to RNA vaccines. *Methods Mol Biol.* **2017**;1499:1–11.
15. Geall AJ, Verma A, Otten GR, *et al.* Nonviral delivery of self-amplifying RNA vaccines. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A.* **2012**;109(36):14604–14609. Lipid nanoparticles are used for delivery of SAM vaccines.
16. Fros JJ, Pijlman GP. Alphavirus infection: host cell shut-off and inhibition of antiviral responses. *Viruses.* **2016**;8(6):166.
17. Bernstein DI, Reap EA, Katen K, *et al.* Randomized, double-blind, phase 1 trial of an alphavirus replicon vaccine for cytomegalovirus in CMV seronegative adult volunteers. *Vaccine.* **2009**;28(2):484–493.
18. Martinon F, Krishnan S, Lenzen G, *et al.* Induction of virus-specific cytotoxic T lymphocytes *in vivo* by liposome-entrapped mRNA. *Eur J Immunol.* **1993**;23(7):1719–1722.
19. Brito LA, Chan M, Shaw CA, *et al.* A cationic nanoemulsion for the delivery of next-generation RNA vaccines. *Mol Ther.* **2014**;22 (12):2118–2129.
20. Kübler H, Scheel B, Gnad-Vogt U, *et al.* Self-adjuvanted mRNA vaccination in advanced prostate cancer patients: a first-in-man phase I/IIa study. *J Immunother Cancer.* **2015**;3:26.
21. Knudsen ML, Ljungberg K, Kakoulidou M, *et al.* Kinetic and phenotypic analysis of CD8⁺ T cell responses after priming with alphavirus replicons and homologous or heterologous booster immunizations. *J Virol.* **2014**;88(21):12438–12451

22. Petsch B, Schnee M, Vogel AB, et al. Protective efficacy of in vitro synthesized, specific mRNA vaccines against influenza A virus infection. *Nat Biotechnol.* **2012**;30(12):1210–1216.
23. Chahal JS, Khan OF, Cooper CL, et al. Dendrimer-RNA nanoparticles generate protective immunity against lethal Ebola, H1N1 influenza, and *Toxoplasma gondii* challenges with a single dose. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A.* **2016**;113(29):E4133–4142.
24. Richner JM, Himansu S, Dowd KA, et al. Modified mRNA vaccines protect against Zika virus infection. *Cell.* **2017**;169(1):176.
25. Magini D, Giovani C, Mangiavacchi S, et al. Self-amplifying mRNA vaccines expressing multiple conserved influenza antigens confer protection against homologous and heterosubtypic viral challenge. *PLoS One.* **2016**;11(8):e0161193.
26. Prioritizing Diseases for Research and Development in Emergency Contexts. Available online: <https://www.who.int/activities/prioritizing-diseases-for-research-and-development-in-emergency-contexts> (accessed on 5 January 2021).
27. An R&D Blueprint for Action to Prevent Epidemics. Report to the Scientific Advisory Group. 2017. Available online: <https://www.who.int/blueprint/about/sag-8feb-ppt.pdf?ua=1> (accessed on 5 January 2021).
28. Polack, F.P.; Thomas, S.J.; Kitchin, N.; Absalon, J.; Gurtman, A.; Lockhart, S.; Perez, J.L.; Pérez Marc, G.; Moreira, E.D.; Zerbini, C.; et al. Safety and efficacy of the BNT162b2 mRNA Covid-19 vaccine. *N. Engl. J. Med.* **2020**, 383, 2603–2615. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
29. Baden, L.R.; El Sahly, H.M.; Essink, B.; Kotloff, K.; Frey, S.; Novak, R.; Diemert, D.; Spector, S.A.; Rouphael, N.; Creech, C.B.; et al. Efficacy and safety of the mRNA-1273 SARS-CoV-2 vaccine. *N. Engl. J. Med.* **2020**. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
30. FDA Takes Key Action in Fight Against COVID-19 By Issuing Emergency Use Authorization for First COVID-19 Vaccine. 2020. Available online: <https://www.fda.gov/news-events/press-announcements/fda-takes-key-action-fight-against-covid-19-issuing-emergency-use-authorization-first-covid-19> (accessed on 5 January 2021).
31. FDA Takes Additional Action in Fight Against COVID-19 By Issuing Emergency Use Authorization for Second COVID-19 Vaccine. 2020. Available online: <https://www.fda.gov/news-events/press-announcements/fda-takes-additional-action-fight-against-covid-19-issuing-emergency-use-authorization-second-covid-19> (accessed on 5 January 2021).
32. WHO Issues Its First Emergency Use Validation for a COVID-19 Vaccine and Emphasizes Need for Equitable Global Access. 2020. Available online: <https://www.who.int/news/item/31-12-2020-who-issues-its-first-emergency-use-validation-for-a-covid-19-vaccine-and-emphasizes-need-for-equitable-global-access> (accessed on 5 January 2021).
33. Wolff, J.A.; Malone, R.W.; Williams, P.; Chong, W.; Acsadi, G.; Jani, A.; Felgner, P.L. Direct gene transfer into mouse muscle in vivo. *Science* **1990**, 247, 1465–1468. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
34. Karikó, K.; Buckstein, M.; Ni, H.; Weissman, D. Suppression of RNA recognition by toll-like receptors: The impact of nucleoside modification and the evolutionary origin of RNA. *Immunity* **2005**, 23, 165–175. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
35. Karikó, K.; Muramatsu, H.; Welsh, F.A.; Ludwig, J.; Kato, H.; Akira, S.; Weissman, D. Incorporation of pseudouridine into mRNA yields superior nonimmunogenic vector with increased translational capacity and biological stability. *Mol. Ther. J. Am. Soc. Gene Ther.* **2008**, 16, 1833–1840. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
36. Thess, A.; Grund, S.; Mui, B.L.; Hope, M.J.; Baumhof, P.; Fotin-Mleczek, M.; Schlake, T. Sequence-engineered mRNA without chemical nucleoside modifications enables an effective protein therapy in large animals. *Mol. Ther. J. Am. Soc. Gene Ther.* **2015**, 23, 1456–1464. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
37. Reichmuth, A.M.; Oberli, M.A.; Jaklenec, A.; Langer, R.; Blankschtein, D. mRNA vaccine delivery using lipid nanoparticles. *Ther. Deliv.* **2016**, 7, 319–334. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
38. Almeida, A.J.; Souto, E. Solid lipid nanoparticles as a drug delivery system for peptides and proteins. *Adv. Drug Deliv. Rev.* **2007**, 59, 478–490. [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
39. Poveda, C.; Biter, A.B.; Bottazzi, M.E.; Strych, U. Establishing preferred product characterization for the evaluation of RNA vaccine antigens. *Vaccines* **2019**, in press. [[Google Scholar](#)]
40. Pardi, N.; Hogan, M.J.; Porter, F.W.; Weissman, D. mRNA vaccines—A new era in vaccinology. *Nat. Rev. Drug Discov.* **2018**, 17, 261–279. [[Google Scholar](#)] [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
41. Pollard, C.; De Koker, S.; Saelens, X.; Vanham, G.; Grooten, J. Challenges and advances towards the rational design of mRNA vaccines. *Trends Mol. Med.* **2013**, 19, 705–713. [[Google Scholar](#)] [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
42. Zhang, C.; Maruggi, G.; Shan, H.; Li, J. Advances in mRNA Vaccines for Infectious Diseases. *Front. Immunol.* **2019**, 10, 594. [[Google Scholar](#)] [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)] [[Green Version](#)]

43. Liu, M.A. A Comparison of Plasmid DNA and mRNA as Vaccine Technologies. *Vaccines* **2019**, *7*, 37. [[Google Scholar](#)] [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
44. Sahin, U.; Karikó, K.; Türeci, Ö. mRNA-based therapeutics—Developing a new class of drugs. *Nat. Rev. Drug Discov.* **2014**, *13*, 759–780. [[Google Scholar](#)] [[CrossRef](#)]
45. Maruggi, G.; Zhang, C.; Li, J.; Ulmer, J.B.; Yu, D. mRNA as a Transformative Technology for Vaccine Development to Control Infectious Diseases. *Mol. Ther.* **2019**, *27*, 757–772. [[Google Scholar](#)] [[CrossRef](#)] [[Green Version](#)]
46. Buschmann MD, Carrasco MJ, Alishetty S, Paige M, Alameh MG, Weissman D. Nanomaterial delivery systems for mrna vaccines. *Vaccines (Basel)* 2021;9(1):1.
47. Weng Y, Li C, Yang T, Hu B, Zhang M, Guo S, et al. The challenge and prospect of mrna therapeutics landscape. *Biotechnol Adv* 2020;40:107534.
48. Bloom K, van den Berg F, Arbuthnot P. Self-amplifying rna vaccines for infectious diseases. *Gene Ther* 2021;28(3–4):117–29.
49. (a) Polack FP, ThomasSJ, KitchinN, et al. Safety and efficacy of the BNT162b2 mRNA Covid-19 vaccine. *N Engl J Med* 2020;383(27): 2603–15. (b) Baden LR, ElSahlyHM, EssinkB, et al. Efficacy and safety of the mRNA-1273 SARS-CoV-2 vaccine. *N Engl J Med* 2021;384(5): 403–16. (c) Feldman RA, FuhrR, SmolenovI, et al. mRNA vaccines against H10N8 and H7N9 influenza viruses of pandemic potential are immu- nogenic and well tolerated in healthy adults in phase 1 randomized clinical trials. *Vaccine* 2019;37(25):3326–34.
50. ZaksT. Emergency Use Authorization(EUA) application form RNA- 1273. Available at: <https://www.fda.gov/media/144583/download>. Accessed December 28, 2020.
51. Yasmin, F., Najeeb, H., Naeem, U., Moeed, A., Atif, A. R., Asghar, M. S., Nimri, N., Saleem, M., Bandyopadhyay, D., Krittanawong, C., Fadelallah Eljack, M. M., Tahir, M. J., & Waqar, F. (2023). Adverse events following COVID-19 mRNA vaccines: A systematic review of cardiovascular complication, thrombosis, and thrombocytopenia. *Immunity, inflammation and disease*, *11*(3), e807. <https://doi.org/10.1002/iid3.807>
52. Klein, N. P., Lewis, N., Goddard, K., Fireman, B., Zerbo, O., Hanson, K. E., Donahue, J. G., Kharbanda, E. O., Naleway, A., Nelson, J. C., Xu, S., Yih, W. K., Glanz, J. M., Williams, J. T. B., Hambidge, S. J., Lewin, B. J., Shimabukuro, T. T., DeStefano, F., & Weintraub, E. S. (2021). Surveillance for Adverse Events After COVID-19 mRNA Vaccination. *JAMA*, *326*(14), 1390–1399. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.2021.15072>
53. Lorentzen, C. L., Haanen, J. B., Met, Ö., & Svane, I. M. (2022). Clinical advances and ongoing trials on mRNA vaccines for cancer treatment. *The Lancet. Oncology*, *23*(10), e450–e458. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045\(22\)00372-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045(22)00372-2)
54. Tang, J., Li, M., Zhao, C., Shen, D., Liu, L., Zhang, X., & Wei, L. (2022). Therapeutic DNA Vaccines against HPV-Related Malignancies: Promising Leads from Clinical Trials. *Viruses*, *14*(2), 239. <https://doi.org/10.3390/v14020239>
55. Wang, Y., Zhang, Z., Luo, J., Han, X., Wei, Y., & Wei, X. (2021). mRNA vaccine: a potential therapeutic strategy. *Molecular cancer*, *20*(1), 33. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12943-021-01311-z>
56. Chen, J., Ye, Z., Huang, C., Qiu, M., Song, D., Li, Y., & Xu, Q. (2022). Lipid nanoparticle-mediated lymph node-targeting delivery of mRNA cancer vaccine elicits robust CD8⁺ T cell response. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, *119*(34), e2207841119. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2207841119>
57. Pfizer-BioNTech COVID-19 Vaccine. *US FDA*; Accessed: 2021 January 12. 2021. <https://www.fda.gov/emergency-preparedness-and-response/coronavirus-disease-2019-covid-19/pfizer-biontech-covid-19-vaccine>
58. Comirnaty. *European Medicines Agency*; Accessed: 2021 January 12. 2021. <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/medicines/human/EPAR/comirnaty>
59. Moderna COVID-19 Vaccine. *US FDA*; Accessed: 2021 January 12. 2021. <https://www.fda.gov/emergency-preparedness-and-response/coronavirus-disease-2019-covid-19/moderna-covid-19-vaccine>
60. COVID-19 Vaccine Moderna. *European Medicines Agency*; Accessed: 2021 January 12. 2021. <https://www.ema.europa.eu/en/medicines/human/summaries-opinion/covid-19-vaccine-moderna>
61. Hinz, T.; Kallen, K.; Britten, C.M.; Flamion, B.; Granzer, U.; Hoos, A.; Huber, C.; Khleif, S.; Kreiter, S.; Rammensee, H.-G.; et al. The European regulatory environment of RNA-based vaccines. In *RNA Vaccines: Methods and Protocols*; Methods in Molecular Biology; Kramps, T., Elbers, K., Eds.; Springer: New York, NY, USA, 2017; pp. 203–222. ISBN 978-1-4939-6481-9. [[Google Scholar](#)]

62. Jackson, N.A.C.; Kester, K.E.; Casimiro, D.; Gurunathan, S.; DeRosa, F. The promise of mRNA vaccines: A biotech and industrial perspective. *NPJ Vaccines* **2020**, *5*, 11. [[Google Scholar](#)] [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
63. Naik, R.; Peden, K. Regulatory considerations on the development of mRNA vaccines. *Curr. Top. Microbiol. Immunol.* **2020**, 1–19. [[Google Scholar](#)] [[CrossRef](#)]
64. Coustasse, A.; Kimble, C.; Maxik, K. COVID-19 and Vaccine Hesitancy: A Challenge the United States Must Overcome. *J. Ambul. Care Manag.* **2021**, *44*, 71–75. [[Google Scholar](#)] [[CrossRef](#)]
65. Dubé, E.; Laberge, C.; Guay, M.; Bramadat, P.; Roy, R.; Bettinger, J. Vaccine hesitancy: An overview. *Hum. Vaccines Immunother.* **2013**, *9*, 1763–1773. [[Google Scholar](#)] [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
66. Baldo, V.; Reno, C.; Cocchio, S.; Fantini, M.P. SARS-CoV-2/COVID-19 Vaccines: The Promises and the Challenges Ahead. *Vaccines* **2021**, *9*, 21. [[Google Scholar](#)] [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
67. Al-Rashid, M., Al-Hamad, A., Al-Hamad, A., & Yasin, Y. (2022). Myths, misconceptions, and hesitancy in people residing in Qatar toward mRNA COVID-19 vaccines: An experience exchange from Qatar University health center. *Qatar medical journal*, 2022(2), 20. <https://doi.org/10.5339/qmj.2022.fqac.20>
68. Joslyn, S., Qin, C., Han, J. H., Savelli, S., & Agrawal, N. (2023). Reducing vaccine hesitancy by explaining vaccine science. *Journal of experimental psychology. Applied*, 29(3), 489–528. <https://doi.org/10.1037/xap0000464>
69. Cabanillas, B., & Novak, N. (2021). Allergy to COVID-19 vaccines: A current update. *Allergology international : official journal of the Japanese Society of Allergology*, 70(3), 313–318. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.alit.2021.04.003>
70. Guo C, Manjili MH, Subjeck JR, Sarkar D, Fisher PB, Wang XY. Therapeutic cancer vaccines: past, present, and future. *Adv Cancer Res.* 2013;119:421–75.
71. Panah, B.Y.; Roos, T.; Kunze, M.; Bertsch, F.; Wochner, A.; Rauen, M.; Hoffmann, P. Bioreactor for Rna in Vitro Transcription 2020. U.S. Patent Application No 17/254,853, 28 June 2018. [[Google Scholar](#)]
72. Skok, J.; Megušar, P.; Vodopivec, T.; Pregeljic, D.; Mencin, N.; Korenč, M.; Krušič, A.; Celjar, A.M.; Pavlin, N.; Krušič, J.; et al. Gram-Scale mRNA Production Using a 250-mL Single-Use Bioreactor. *Chem. Ing. Tech.* 2022, *94*, 1928–1935. [[Google Scholar](#)] [[CrossRef](#)]
73. Ouranidis, A.; Vavilis, T.; Mandala, E.; Davidopoulou, C.; Stamoula, E.; Markopoulou, C.K.; Karagianni, A.; Kachrimanis, K. mRNA Therapeutic Modalities Design, Formulation and Manufacturing under Pharma 4.0 Principles. *Biomedicines* 2021, *10*, 50. [[Google Scholar](#)] [[CrossRef](#)]
74. Scheibhofer, S., Thalhamer, J., & Weiss, R. (2018). DNA and mRNA vaccination against allergies. *Pediatric Allergy and Immunology*, 29(7), 679–688.
75. See 172 countries and multiple candidate vaccines engaged in COVID-19 vaccine Global Access Facility, WHO (Aug. 24, 2020), <https://www.who.int/news/item/24-08-2020-172-countries-and-multiple-candidate-vaccines-engaged-in-covid-19-vaccine-global-accessfacility>.
76. Kumar, S.; Thambiraja, T.S.; Karuppanan, K.; Subramaniam, G. Omicron and Delta Variant of SARS-CoV-2: A Comparative Computational Study of Spike Protein. *J. Med. Virol.* **2021**. [[Google Scholar](#)] [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
77. Danese, E.; Montagnana, M.; Salvagno, G.L.; Peserico, D.; Pighi, L.; De Nitto, S.; Henry, B.M.; Porru, S.; Lippi, G. Comprehensive Assessment of Humoral Response after Pfizer BNT162b2 MRNA Covid-19 Vaccination: A Three-Case Series. *Clin. Chem. Lab. Med.* **2021**, *59*, 1585–1591. [[Google Scholar](#)] [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
78. Wisnewski, A.V.; Campillo Luna, J.; Redlich, C.A. Human IgG and IgA Responses to COVID-19 MRNA Vaccines. *PLoS ONE* **2021**, *16*, e0249499. [[Google Scholar](#)] [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
79. Hassan, A.O.; Kafai, N.M.; Dmitriev, I.P.; Fox, J.M.; Smith, B.K.; Harvey, I.B.; Chen, R.E.; Winkler, E.S.; Wessel, A.W.; Case, J.B.; et al. A Single-Dose Intranasal ChAd Vaccine Protects Upper and Lower Respiratory Tracts against SARS-CoV-2. *Cell* **2020**, *183*, 169–184.e13. [[Google Scholar](#)] [[CrossRef](#)] [[PubMed](#)]
80. "Global mRNA Platform Industry", *finance.yahoo.com*, Unknown, <https://finance.yahoo.com/news/global-mrna-platform-industry-132300981.html>, .
81. The efficacy and effectiveness of COVID-19 vaccines around the world: a mini-review and meta-analysis | *Annals of Clinical Microbiology and Antimicrobials* | Full Text", *ann-clinmicrob.biomedcentral.com*, Unknown, <https://ann-clinmicrob.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12941-023-00594-y>, .
82. "Global access to COVID-19 vaccines: a scoping review of factors that may influence equitable access for low and middle-income countries | *BMJ Open*", *bmjopen.bmj.com*, Unknown, <https://bmjopen.bmj.com/content/11/9/e049505>, .

83. Press release: The Nobel Prize in Physiology or Medicine 2023 - NobelPrize.org", *nobelprize.org*, Unknown, <https://www.nobelprize.org/prizes/medicine/2023/press-release/>, .
84. "Global COVID-19 vaccine inequity: The scope, the impact, and the challenges - PMC", *ncbi.nlm.nih.gov*, Unknown, <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8279498/>, .
85. "Vaccination Campaigns - Faster Capital", *fastercapital.com*, Unknown, <https://fastercapital.com/keyword/vaccination-campaigns.html>, .
86. "When will the COVID-19 pandemic end? | McKinsey", *mckinsey.com*, Unknown, <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/healthcare/our-insights/when-will-the-covid-19-pandemic-end>, .
87. "Tracking COVID-19 vaccines and therapeutics | McKinsey", *mckinsey.com*, Unknown, <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/life-sciences/our-insights/on-pins-and-needles-will-covid-19-vaccines-save-the-world>, .
88. Comparing the COVID-19 Vaccines: How Are They Different? > News > Yale Medicine", *yalemedicine.org*, Unknown, <https://www.yalemedicine.org/news/covid-19-vaccine-comparison>, .
89. A Global Effort Accelerates SARS-CoV-2 Vaccines | Epicentre", *epicenter.wcfia.harvard.edu*, Unknown, <https://epicenter.wcfia.harvard.edu/blog/global-effort-accelerates-sars-cov-2-vaccines>, .
90. "Statement for healthcare professionals: How COVID-19 vaccines are regulated for safety and effectiveness (Revised March 2022)", *who.int*, Unknown, <https://www.who.int/news/item/17-05-2022-statement-for-healthcare-professionals-how-covid-19-vaccines-are-regulated-for-safety-and-effectiveness>, .
91. "History of mRNA Vaccines | VWR", *us.vwr.com*, Unknown, <https://us.vwr.com/cms/history-of-mRNA-vaccines>, .
92. "The Promising Pancreatic Cancer Vaccine Clinical Trial", *uhealth.com*, Unknown, <https://www.uhealth.com/en/media-room/articles/pancreatic-cancer-vaccine-clinical-trial-a-new-frontier-in-cancer-treatment>, .
93. "Progress Deferred: Lessons From mRNA Vaccine Development - Institute for Progress", *ifp.org*, Unknown, <https://ifp.org/progress-deferred-lessons-from-mrna-vaccine-development/>, .
94. "COVID-19 Vaccines as Global Common Goods: An Integrated Approach of Ethical, Economic Policy and Intellectual Property Management", *degruyter.com*, Unknown, <https://www.degruyter.com/document/doi/10.1515/gj-2021-0042/html?lang=en>, .
95. "How will vaccines save us from future threats? - IFPMA", *ifpma.org*, Unknown, <https://www.ifpma.org/insights/how-will-vaccines-save-us-from-future-threats/>, .
96. "mRNA Vaccines: a growing and complex IP landscape", *insights.Bio*, Unknown, <https://www.insights.bio/vaccine-insights/journal/article/2569/mRNA-Vaccines-a-growing-and-complex-IP-landscape>, .
97. A Guide to Global COVID-19 Vaccine Efforts | Council on Foreign Relations", *cfr.org*, Unknown, <https://www.cfr.org/backgrounder/guide-global-covid-19-vaccine-efforts>, .
98. "Vaccine nationalism will persist: global public goods need effective engagement of global citizens | Globalization and Health | Full Text", *globalizationandhealth.biomedcentral.com*, Unknown, <https://globalizationandhealth.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12992-022-00802-y>, .